

Influence of annealing temperature on the photocatalytic efficiency of sol-gel dip-coated ZnO thin films in methyl orange degradation

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ABSTRACT

ZnO thin films on glass substrates and silicon wafers were prepared by the sol-gel dipcoating technique and annealed at temperatures ranging from 300 - 550 °C. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Raman analysis confirm the hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) examination confirmed that the films were homogeneous, crack-free and with a uniform distribution of nano-sized spherical grains. The decomposition of methyl orange (MO) using a solar simulator was used to determine the photocatalytic activity of the thin films. The annealing temperature was found to have a significant influence on the structure, morphology, and photocatalytic performance of ZnO thin films. The best photocatalytic activity under solar irradiation was shown by the ZnO thin film annealed at 450 °C. The enhanced photocatalytic performance of the films can be attributed to their optimized crystallinity, surface roughness and morphology, which provide more active sites for the photocatalytic reactions.

1. Introduction

Water and air pollution are global environmental concerns, but their severity and consequences may differ depending on the regions and nations. Lancet Commission on pollution and health reported that approximately 9 million deaths (accounting for 16% of all global deaths) were attributed to pollution in 2015 using data from the Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study [1]. The Commission reported in 2022 that 92% of pollution-related deaths and most economic losses occurred in low-income and middle-income countries [2]. Numerous water sources, such as rivers, lakes, and oceans, are subjected to pollution originating from diverse sources, including industrial discharge, sewage, improper waste disposal, and the release of toxic dyes. Therefore, there has been a growing interest in utilizing photocatalysis for water treatment, owing to its ability to entirely degrade organic pollutants and its wide applicability to diverse compounds.

Although TiO₂ is the best known photocatalyst, the use of ZnO is also growing. ZnO is an n-type semiconductor that commonly crystallizes in a hexagonal wurtzite structure, with a direct band gap of 3.37 eV and a large exciton binding energy of 60 meV [3]. Recent studies have shown

that ZnO exhibits higher photoactivity than TiO₂ due to its higher quantum efficiency and mineralization rates [4–6]. Based on mobility, photocatalysts can be categorized into two types: mobilized photocatalysts (in powder form) and immobilized photocatalysts (thin films). Immobilized photoelectrodes are more cost-effective and can be easily recycled through washing compared to mobilized ones, which face challenges in recycling and aggregation due to the high loading of powder photocatalysts [7]. Some studies have focused on the synthesis of highly photocatalytic ZnO nanoparticles, powders, and colloids [8,9]. In some cases, coatings in photoreactors were prepared using ZnO powder deposition [10]. However, the method is not suitable for self-cleaning windows due to the low transparency of the coating. There are also difficulties with the application in continuous flow systems, such as in photocatalytic reactors, since the reactants may not be adequately exposed to the catalyst. [11,12]. Thin film photocatalysts offer several advantages over powder photocatalysts, such as reduced material usage, elimination of costly recycling and recollection processes after degradation, quick electron transport, homogenous exposure of the photocatalyst, effective solar energy absorption, improved long-term performance, and simple tuning of material properties [13,

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14].

Several methodologies have been employed for the synthesis of ZnO films, including pulsed laser deposition (PLD) [15], chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [16], molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) [17], magnetron sputtering [18,19], and sol-gel [20–22]. Among these, the sol-gel method has provided a cost-effective and facile deposition process, facilitating the production of large-area, high-quality ZnO films [8,11]. The photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films depends on different factors such as synthesis parameters (solvent, additives, and pH) of ZnO sol, deposition techniques, annealing temperature, the addition of dopants, as well as the combination of ZnO with other semiconductors as a co-catalyst [23]. Among these, annealing temperature is one of the most important factors which affects the physicochemical properties of coatings. It affects several properties, such as the crystalline phase structure of the photocatalyst, the surface morphology of the photocatalytic coatings, and their mechanical stability, which are directly related to their photocatalytic activity [14,24]. There are very few reports describing the effect of annealing temperature on the photocatalytic performance of ZnO thin films prepared by the sol-gel method. For instance, Jongnavakit et al. reported that the photocatalytic efficiency of methylene blue degradation under ultra-violet (UV) light was better with the ZnO thin films annealed at higher temperatures, attributed to the improvement in the crystallinity and a high surface roughness. [11]. Another similar study done by Lv et al. reported that the increase of temperature from 400 to 800 °C resulted in an increment in photocatalytic activity, mainly due to the formation of oxygen defects in ZnO crystals [25].

In this study, the ZnO thin films on glass substrates were prepared by the sol-gel dip coating method and annealed at temperatures ranging from 300 °C to 550 °C using an increment of 10 °C/min. The structural properties and photocatalytic performance of ZnO thin films were studied through the degradation of methylene orange (MO) as a function of sintering temperature. Previous studies mainly focused on UV light activation to generate reactive oxygen species [3,20,22,25–28]. However, photocatalysis under solar irradiation has not been extensively reported. This study focuses on the development of ZnO thin films by optimizing their annealing temperature and investigating their photocatalytic performance using a solar simulator.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Preparation and deposition of ZnO sol

A stable and transparent ZnO sol was obtained by sol-gel method. First, 4.37 g of zinc acetate dihydrate (ZAD, Sigma Aldrich, 98%, Germany) was dissolved in 18.19 g of ethanol (EtOH, Sigma Aldrich, 99%, Germany) under continuous stirring at 60 °C for 1 h. To attain the complete dissolution of ZAD in EtOH, 2.07 g of diethanolamine (DEA, Sigma Aldrich, 99%, Germany) was slowly incorporated into the first solution at room temperature. After 1h of stirring, a transparent and homogeneous ZnO sol was obtained. The sol was aged for 24 h before being deposited on glass substrates and Si wafers.

Thin films of ZnO were deposited on soda-lime glass substrates and Si wafers pre-cleaned with soap-water and ethanol. The soda-lime glass was previously coated with a silica sol, following the process described in the literature [29]. The SiO₂ coating inhibits the diffusion of alkaline ions from the soda-lime glass to the ZnO coating during heat treatment, thus avoiding the probable suppression of photocatalytic activity [30]. The ZnO deposition was performed by the dip-coating method using a withdrawal rate of 25 cm/min, as higher rates caused the coatings to crack. After dip coating, the layers were dried at 80 °C for 1 h and then sintered at 300, 400, 450, 500, and 550 °C for 1 h using a heating rate of 10 °C /min.

2.2. Characterizations of the ZnO thin films

Various characterization techniques were used to study the compositional, structural, and morphological properties, and photocatalytic activity of ZnO. The molecular structure of ZnO sol was studied using a Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (PerkinElmer spectrum 100, USA) in the range of 4000 – 450 cm⁻¹ using 16 scans with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The measurements were conducted in ATR mode, and appropriate corrections were applied to the acquired spectra. After annealing the thin films at different temperatures, the phase purity and the crystal structure of the thin films on Si-wafers were analyzed using X-ray diffraction (D8 advance Bruker, Germany) working with a copper source (CuK_{α1} radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) in the diffraction angles range of $20^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 70^\circ$. The microstructure and the surface morphology of the ZnO thin films on glass-slide substrates were examined using scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, LEO- Zeiss, Germany). The average grain size was estimated using ImageJ software from FE-SEM images. Atomic force microscope (AFM) images of the ZnO thin films on glass-slide substrates were obtained by scanning over a surface area of $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ using a Bruker Innova microscope at room temperature and humidity. The measurements were carried out in tapping mode at a frequency of 300 kHz, using RTESPA-300 tip. The films on Si-wafers annealed at different temperatures were also characterized by Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectra were measured using Raman Microscope Horiba Scientific, Xplora Plus, Japan, in the range of 200 to 1000 cm⁻¹, using the 514.5 nm excitation wavelength from an Ar ion laser.

The elemental composition and chemical state of ZnO thin films on Si-wafers were studied using XPS analysis (Thermo Scientific Nexsa G2, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) in the range of 0 –1100 eV using a monochromatic Al-K_α radiation (1486.8 eV) with a spot size of 100 μm and pass energy of 280 eV. The Advantage (Thermo Scientific) software was used to process spectrum data. The transmittance in the range of 350–800 nm was also measured to study the optical properties of the thin films on glass-slide substrates using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer Lambda 950 Inc., USA). The thickness of the ZnO coatings were measured using a spectroscopic ellipsometer in the wavelength range of 350–800 nm and using a M-2000UTM ellipsometer (J.A. Woollam Co., Lincoln, NE, USA). The incidence angle varied between 50 and 60°, and the data was acquired over a period of 10 s and modeled using Complete EASE software (version 5.20, J.A. Woollam Co.).

2.3. Photocatalytic dye degradation: procedure and measurement setup

Photocatalytic activity of the thin films was studied using a solar simulator. An aqueous solution of 25 mL with a methyl orange (MO) dye concentration of 3 mg/L at pH = 7 was used to study the degradation efficiency of the ZnO thin film photocatalysts. The area of exposure of the ZnO coating on the glass substrates was about 25 cm². The catalyst was vertically placed in the middle of the MO solution in a rectangular quartz vessel and covered using a soda lime glass to avoid evaporation of MO due to heat from the light source: thus, a constant volume of the solution was maintained throughout the process.

The solar simulator used (Oriel model 96,000) is equipped with a solar-simulating Xe-arc lamp (Osram XBO 450 W) and a 6197AM 1.5 filter to adjust the spectral output of a light source to mimic the solar spectrum. The components are arranged in such a way that a low bandpass filter with a center at 500 nm and a bandwidth of 10 nm (Thorlabs, FB-500-10 full width at half maximum) was positioned beyond the sample and in front of a biased Silicon Photodetector (Thorlabs DET100A). The quartz holder was filled with the sample, and the MO covered with glass was kept under a magnetic stirrer. The filter limits the light transmission in a wavelength range matching the absorption band of the MO. Consequently, the light intensity at the detector enables the degradation of MO to be measured. All the components were arranged on a rigid table for stability and were optically isolated in the dark to prevent the presence of additional light

sources. A Keithley 2010 multimeter was connected to the detector's output signal (voltage). The signal at the multimeter was recorded every 10 min using Visual Basic code on a personal computer. More information about experimental setup has been previously described by Y. Castro et al. [30]. The degree of photocatalytic degradation (in percent) was determined by applying the formula expressed in Eq. (1.1)

$$\text{Percentage photodegradation} = \frac{A_0 - A}{A_0} \times 100 \quad (1.1)$$

where A_0 denotes the initial absorbance of dye, and A denotes the absorbance of dye after photodegradation at each interval.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural studies of ZnO thin film

Fig. 1(a) shows the FTIR spectra of diethanolamine (DEA), zinc acetate dihydrate (ZAD), ZAD+EtOH+DEA after immediate addition of DEA, and the final ZnO sol. In all spectra, characteristic absorption bands corresponding to the O–H stretching vibrations and attributed to the hydration of water molecules were identified around 3294 and 3298 cm^{-1} . On the other hand, bands at 2833, 2908, and 2973 cm^{-1} , assigned to asymmetric and symmetric C–H bonds, were also identified in DEA, ZAD+EtOH+DEA, and ZnO sol spectra [31]. Vafaei et al. reported that the presence of these C–H bonds in the ZAD+EtOH+DEA solution and the ZnO sol are associated with the formation of monoacetate group intermediates, similar to what was observed in this study. (Eq.1.2) [32]. The peaks at 1451, 1435, 1409, and 1406 cm^{-1} attributed to C–H bending vibrations, and the bands at 1048 and 1046 cm^{-1} to C–N stretching vibration were also identified in the DEA, ZAD+EtOH+DEA, and ZnO sol spectra [33]. The peak at 1554 cm^{-1} identified in the ZAD spectrum and attributed to the C = O stretching vibrations, shifted to 1572 cm^{-1} in the ZAD+EtOH+DEA spectrum and 1570 cm^{-1} in the final ZnO sol spectrum, corroborating the formation of the intermediate monoacetate complex (Eq. (1.3)). Thus, considering the FTIR spectra, the following reactions are suggested [34].

On the other hand, a small peak at $\sim 429 - 427 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was observed in the ZAD+EtOH+DEA solution and ZnO sol spectra and attributed to Zn–O bonds.

Then, ZnO coatings were prepared by immersion on glass-slides and treated at temperatures between 300 - 550 $^\circ\text{C}$. The ZnO coatings were scraped off and the powders obtained at 300, 400, 450, 500, and 550 $^\circ\text{C}$ were subsequently analyzed using FTIR, as shown in Fig. 1(b). For the ZnO annealed at temperatures higher than 400 $^\circ\text{C}$, a unique sharp peak was identified at 429 cm^{-1} , indicating the crystallization of ZnO. In the case of low annealing temperature, peaks in the range 3750- 3000 cm^{-1} and 1700 - 600 cm^{-1} appear associated with organic species together with hydroxyl groups that have not been removed.

XRD analysis of ZnO thin films on Si wafers pre-heated at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ and heat treated at different temperatures (300, 400, 450, 500, and 550 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h) are shown in Fig. 2(a). The X-ray reflections at 2θ angles of 31.92 $^\circ$, 34.52 $^\circ$, 36.44 $^\circ$, 47.84 $^\circ$, and 56.80 $^\circ$ from (100), (002), (101), (102) and (110) planes shown in Fig. 2(a) are consistent with the polycrystalline hexagonal wurtzite ZnO structure (ICDD data card 98–001–1316) [35]. The Scherrer equation was employed to provide the average size on the coherently diffracting domains (crystallites) of the ZnO films [36]. Fig. 2(b) shows the relationship between annealing temperature and the crystallite size and full width at half maximum (FWHM) of ZnO thin films. The crystal size increases with annealing temperature, while the FWHM decreases with increasing annealing temperature [37], indicating that the crystallinity of ZnO is improved with treatment.

Raman spectroscopy was employed to investigate the structure of the ZnO thin films deposited on Si wafers treated at 400, 450, and 500 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. The spectra are shown in Fig. S1. The peak at 433 cm^{-1} is typical of hexagonal ZnO, which is the E_2 (high) mode associated with oxygen atoms in ZnO [38]. The prominent peaks at 526 cm^{-1} and the peaks at 301, 615, 820, and 973 cm^{-1} in all spectra are assigned to Si substrate [39]. All films treated at various temperatures exhibit characteristic Raman peaks of the wurtzite structure of ZnO, in line with the XRD results.

XPS analysis was performed to confirm the chemical composition of the ZnO thin films. Fig. S2 illustrates the XPS spectra of the ZnO films deposited on Si-wafer and annealed at different temperatures, and the peaks are assigned to the signals of C, Zn, and O elements. The low-intensity C peaks are caused by the adsorption of organic contaminants during sample preparation and handling under ambient conditions. The XPS survey spectrum confirms that the primary constituents are zinc and oxygen and indicates that the synthesized ZnO thin film deposited on Si-wafer is free from any external impurities. The atomic

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of DEA, ZAD, ZAD+EtOH+DEA (after DEA addition) and ZnO sol (a) and FTIR spectra of ZnO powders at different temperatures (b).

Fig. 2. XRD of ZnO thin films annealed at different temperatures (a) and variation of crystallite size and FWHM with the annealing temperature (b).

percentage for ZnO thin film annealed at different temperature is given in Table S1.

The core-level spectra of Zn2p were analyzed in detail, Fig. 3(a): the peaks observed at 1021.5 eV and 1044.6 eV are attributed to Zn2p_{3/2} and Zn2p_{1/2} binding energies, respectively, consistent with the values previously reported in the literature [40,41]. The 23 eV splitting for Zn2p_{1/2} and Zn2p_{3/2} confirms that the Zn atoms are in a fully oxidized state. As the annealing temperature increases, the splitting of Zn2p_{3/2} and Zn2p_{1/2} peaks shifts slightly towards lower binding energies (~ 0.3 eV), associated with the reduction in the number of oxygen vacancies and the presence of zinc defects at higher temperatures [42].

Fig. 3(b–f) shows the core-level of O1s XPS spectra of ZnO thin films. The asymmetric O1s peak could be fitted by two components representing two different states: (1) O²⁻ in a wurtzite structure surrounded by Zn atoms at low binding energy of 530.1 eV (O–Zn) and (2) OH

species and/or aqueous species adsorbed on the surface of ZnO film at high binding energy of 531.5 eV (–O–H) associated with oxygen vacancies [43]. The role of oxygen vacancies in photocatalytic activity is a topic of ongoing debate. Some researchers have suggested that these surface defects are beneficial in enhancing photocatalytic activity by promoting charge separation and improving UV light utilization [44, 45]. The presence of oxygen vacancies can also mediate interface charge transfer, thus facilitating photocatalytic processes [46]. On the other hand, other studies have also reported that excessive oxygen vacancies might impair photocatalytic efficiency by disrupting the electronic structure of ZnO [47–49]. As shown in Fig. 3(b–f), the intensity associated with Zn–OH groups decreased with increasing annealing temperature, indicating a reduction in the number of hydroxyl groups on the surface. In this work, the reduction of hydroxyl groups and the increment of O–Zn peak intensity at higher annealing temperatures could

Fig. 3. Core level XPS spectra of Zn2p orbital peaks annealed at different temperatures (a) and core level O1s XPS spectra of ZnO thin films annealed at the temperatures of 300 (b), 400 (c), 450 (d), 500 (e), and 550 (f) °C.

promote a balance between maintaining sufficient oxygen vacancies for effective photocatalysis and reducing the excess surface hydroxyl groups. This balance is important for optimizing the photocatalytic performance of ZnO thin films [25,41,46].

Fig. 4 shows SEM images of ZnO films after annealing at various temperatures. ZnO nanoparticles exhibit irregular to nearly spherical shapes. The coatings show a small number of pores and no cracks. At 300 °C and 400 °C, the films show smooth surfaces with poorly defined grains [50]. As the annealing temperature increases from 450 °C to 500 °C, the grains become more distinct and better defined. At 550 °C, the film shows signs of grain coarsening [22]. The average grain size of ZnO increases from ~10 to ~50 nm as the annealing temperature is raised from 300 to 550 °C. In Fig. 4(f), the higher magnification SEM image provides a more detailed view of the film annealed at 550 °C. Additional images are shown in Fig. S3.

The two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) AFM images of ZnO thin films on glass substrate annealed at various temperatures are shown in Fig. 5. The root mean square roughness (Rms) values of the ZnO thin films obtained from AFM images are listed in Table 1: the roughness of the ZnO thin film increases with increasing annealing temperature as a result of the coalescence of smaller crystallites into larger grains at higher temperatures [51].

Fig. 6. shows the thickness of the ZnO thin films treated at various temperatures. The figure shows that thickness decreases from ~278 nm to 210 nm as temperature increases from 300 °C to 500 °C, reaching a minimum of around 500 °C, attributed to the densification of the ZnO thin film and the removal of the organic precursors, leading to a more compact structure. However, at temperatures above 500 °C, grain growth and the formation of an interfacial layer between the ZnO and the substrate may contribute to the slight increase in thickness. This trend aligns with previous observations, where densification processes dominate at moderate annealing temperatures, while grain coarsening and interlayer formation become more prominent at higher temperatures [22,25].

The transmittance spectra of ZnO thin films annealed at various temperatures are shown in Fig. 7(a), together with the ZnO thin films photographs. All ZnO thin films exhibit transmittance values above 80% across the whole visible wavelength range. The transmittance at 550 nm

for uncoated glass and ZnO thin films annealed from 300 – 550 °C is 90.9, 85.9, 92.6, 94.9, 95.5 and 85.6 %, respectively. For the ZnO thin film annealed at 300 °C, significant absorption is observed between 350 and 500 nm, probably due to the presence of incomplete crystallization of ZnO and the presence of organic residues or hydroxyl groups. ZnO thin films with many grain boundaries or small grain sizes tend to exhibit high optical scattering, leading to lower transmittance. As the annealing temperature increases, particle size increases, which reduces grain boundaries and thus leads to increase in transmittance [26,52]. However, at 550 °C, a slight reduction in transmittance is observed compared to the 500 °C sample. This reduction may be attributed to grain coarsening or the formation of a Si-Zn-oxide interlayer, which can increase light scattering and reduce transparency [11,22]. These observations are consistent with the SEM and XRD analysis.

The direct energy band-gap of ZnO thin films was estimated using the Tauc plot method, Fig. 7(b). The figure plots of $(ah\nu)^2$ against photon energy ($h\nu$) here a is the absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ is the photon energy, and k is a proportionality constant. For a direct band-gap material like ZnO, the relationship between α and the energy band-gap (E_g) is given by:

$$(ah\nu)^2 = k(h\nu - E_g) \quad (1.4)$$

The energy band-gap is determined by extrapolating the linear region of the $(ah\nu)^2$ of each plot towards lower photon energies. The results indicate that the film annealed at 300 °C has a lower band gap compared to ZnO films annealed at higher temperatures. This lower band gap (3.25 eV) can be attributed to the presence of high defect density [53]. The band-gap values of the ZnO thin films annealed at 400–550 °C are almost same (~3.28 eV), similar to other reported papers [53,54].

3.2. Photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films

Initially, the absorbance spectrum of MO was monitored for 60 min. No significant changes in the absorbance values were observed, indicating that photolysis of MO does not occur under radiation of solar simulation, as shown in the inset of Fig. 8(a). Photocatalytic tests were conducted on ZnO thin films annealed at various temperatures (400 to

Fig. 4. SEM images of ZnO thin films annealed at different temperatures: (a) 300, (b) 400, (c) 450, (d) 500, and (e) 550 °C and (f) the ZnO films annealed at 550 °C at a higher magnification.

Fig. 5. 2D and 3D AFM images of ZnO thin films annealed at different temperatures.

Table 1

AFM roughness (R_{rms}) of ZnO thin films annealed at different temperatures.

Annealing temperature (°C)	R_{rms} (nm)
300	2.05 ± 0.1
400	2.78 ± 0.2
450	4.09 ± 0.1
500	4.30 ± 0.3
550	5.09 ± 0.5

Fig. 6. Variation of thickness of ZnO thin film with annealing temperatures.

550 °C). Fig. 8(a) illustrates the relationship between the percentual degradation of MO over time for films annealed at different temperatures. The results indicate that the thin films annealed at 450 °C and 500 °C exhibit the highest photocatalytic activity, achieving over 90% MO degradation within 300 min. This performance is 25% better than that of the film annealed at 550 °C; the latter exhibits only a 70% degradation rate at the same time. On the other hand, the kinetic model of the photocatalytic degradation of MO was analyzed using the pseudo-first-order Langmuir–Hinshelwood model, which is described by Eq. (1.5) [55]:

$$[\ln(C_0/C)] = kt \quad (1.5)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration, C is the concentration at time t , and k is the rate constant (min^{-1}). The plots of $\ln(C_0/C)$ vs. time, t , resulted in

a straight line, with the slope representing the rate constant k (Fig. 8(b)). The linear nature of the plot for all ZnO films indicates that the photocatalytic degradation of MO follows a pseudo-first-order reaction rate. The value of k is directly related to the photocatalytic efficiency; higher values indicate higher efficiency, Table 2 [56]. ZnO thin film annealed at 450 °C exhibits the highest photocatalytic activity.

Some studies report that high crystallinity and roughness can enhance photocatalytic activity [11,25]. As seen from AFM, surface roughness increases, and from XRD, crystallinity improves with increasing temperature. The reduced photocatalytic activity observed in the film annealed at 400 °C may be attributed to incomplete removal of organic reactants used in the synthesis, leading to incomplete ZnO formation. Moreover, the less-defined grains observed by SEM confirm that the lower photocatalytic activity can also be attributed to the reduced active surface area. The films annealed at 450 °C and 500 °C exhibit well-defined grains and high crystallinity, leading to high photocatalytic activity. Although the final degradation is similar for both thin films annealed at 450 °C and 500 °C, the ZnO thin film annealed at 450 °C degrades 50% of MO after 50 min of irradiation, whereas the ZnO thin film annealed at 500 °C degrades only 40%. The optimal surface structure formed at these two annealing temperatures provides more active sites for photocatalytic reactions. However, the thin film annealed at the highest temperature (550 °C) shows lower photocatalytic activity than the others. The film contains larger grains with signs of grain coarsening, leading to reduced active surface area and possible agglomerations or defects that negatively impact photocatalytic performance. Also, Torres Delgado et al. reported that the annealing of ZnO thin films at temperatures exceeding 500 °C may impair photocatalytic properties due to the formation of an amorphous compound composed of Si, Zn, and O at the interface of the coating and the substrate [22].

According to the principles of photocatalysis, reactions in ZnO take place when light radiation of energy ($h\nu$) that matches or exceeds the ZnO band gap energy ($h\nu \geq E_g$) is absorbed. Upon photoactivation of ZnO, electrons (e^-) within the valence band transition to the conduction band, leaving behind holes (h^+) in the valence band. This formation of photogenerated e^- - h^+ pairs, as represented in Eq. (1.6), enables their migration to the ZnO surface, where they actively participate in redox reactions, as illustrated in Eq. (1.7) to 1.9. Specifically, H^+ ions take place in reactions with water and hydroxide ions to generate hydroxyl radicals, while electrons react with oxygen to form superoxide radical anions and, subsequently, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), as represented in Eq. (1.10). H_2O_2 , in turn, interacts with superoxide radicals to yield hydroxyl radicals (Eq. (1.11)-(1.14)). These hydroxyl radicals, known for their potent oxidizing properties, subsequently attack pollutants adsorbed on the ZnO surface, resulting in a rapid production of intermediary compounds. Ultimately, these intermediates undergo

Fig. 7. Transmittance spectra (a) and energy band-gap (b) of ZnO thin films annealed at different temperatures.

Fig. 8. Photodegradation curves (a) and kinetics model (b) of MO degradation using ZnO thin films as photocatalyst annealed at various temperatures.

Table 2

First-order rate constants (k) for the photocatalytic degradation of MO by ZnO thin films annealed at different temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	Rate constant (k)
400	0.005
450	0.009
500	0.008
550	0.004

conversion into environmentally friendly substances, including CO_2 , H_2O , and mineral acids, as expressed in Eq. (1.16). Consequently, the mechanism underlying the photodegradation of organic compounds in the presence of solar radiation via redox reactions is summarized in equations (Eq. (1.6)-1.16) [57,58].

Table 3 compares the photocatalytic performance of ZnO films prepared using sol-gel method by different authors. The degradation efficiency obtained by the ZnO film treated at 450 °C is slightly higher than the values reported by other authors. Therefore, further improvements could be made by using strategies such as doping to enhance photocatalytic performance under solar light [59–62].

4. Conclusions

ZnO thin films on glass-slide and Si wafers were prepared by sol-gel method and then annealed at different temperatures from 300 to 550 °C.

Table 3
Comparison of photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films prepared by sol-gel method.

Number of layers	Thickness (nm)	Annealing temperature (°C)	Light source	Time of irradiation (h)	Model pollutant	Degradation (%)	Ref.
1	Not given	500	UV	5	MB	85	[22]
10	500	500	UV	3	MB	70	[63]
40	335	500	UV	5	MB	82	[3]
1	250	600	UV	4	Rhodamine-B	50	[64]
7	250	450	UV	3	MB	60	[65]
1	210	450	Solar simulator	5	MO	94	Present study

FTIR spectroscopy confirmed Zn-O bond formation, while XRD and Raman spectra analyses identified the hexagonal wurtzite structure with enhanced crystallinity at higher annealing temperatures. SEM and AFM studies showed well-defined grains and increased surface roughness, respectively, which contribute to improved photocatalytic activity. The optimal photocatalytic activity observed at 450 °C aligns with the changes in surface composition, indicating a balance between Zn-OH and Zn-O states that favors the enhancement of the photocatalytic effect. Photocatalytic tests indicated that films annealed at 450 °C and 500 °C achieved the highest degradation efficiency for methyl orange dye, exceeding 90% in 300 min. Lower activity at 400 °C was attributed to incomplete ZnO formation, while the grain coarsening due to the annealing effect hindered photocatalytic performance of ZnO thin film annealed at 550 °C. These studies show the importance of annealing conditions in improving ZnO thin film properties for photocatalytic application in solar simulating conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

A.H. Haritha: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **M.E. Cruz:** Supervision, Data curation. **O. Sisman:** Data curation. **A. Duran:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **D. Galusek:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **J.J. Velázquez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Y. Castro:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The author is an Editorial Board Member/Editor-in-Chief/Associate Editor/Guest Editor for [*Journal name*] and was not involved in the editorial review or the decision to publish this article.

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Supplementary materials

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References

- [1] P.J. Landrigan, R. Fuller, N.J.R. Acosta, O. Adeyi, R. Arnold, N.(Nil) Basu, A. B. Baldé, R. Bertollini, S. Bose-O'Reilly, J.I. Boufford, P.N. Breyse, T. Chiles, C. Mahidol, A.M. Coll-Seck, P.M.L. Cropper, J. Fobil, V. Fuster, M. Greenstone, A. Haines, D. Hanrahan, D. Hunter, M. Khare, A. Krupnick, B. Lanphear, B. Lohani, K. Martin, K.V. Mathiasen, M.A. McTeer, C.J.L. Murray, J.D. Ndahimananjara, F. Perera, J. Potočnik, A.S. Preker, The Lancet Commission on pollution and health, *Lancet* 391 (2018) 462–512, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32345-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32345-0).
- [2] R. Fuller, P.J. Landrigan, K. Balakrishnan, G. Bathan, S. Bose-O'Reilly, M. Brauer, J. Caravanos, T. Chiles, A. Cohen, L. Corra, P.M. Cropper, G. Ferraro, J. Hanna, D. Hanrahan, H. Hu, D. Hunter, G. Janata, R. Kupka, B. Lanphear, M. Lichtveld, K. Martin, A. Mustapha, E. Sanchez-Triana, K. Sandilya, L. Schaefli, J. Shaw, Pollution and health: a progress update, *Lancet Planet. Heal.* 6 (2022) e535–e547, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00090-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00090-0).
- [3] S. Alavi, H. Bazrafshan, M. Nikazar, An investigation into the simultaneous influence of withdrawal speed and number of coated layers on photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 81 (2017) 652–661, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-016-4230-x>.
- [4] A.N. Rao, B. Sivasankar, V. Sadasivam, Kinetic study on the photocatalytic degradation of salicylic acid using ZnO catalyst, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 166 (2009) 1357–1361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2008.12.051>.
- [5] Y. Castro, N. Arconada, A. Durán, Synthesis and photocatalytic characterisation of mesoporous TiO₂ films doped with Ca, W and N, *Bol. La Soc. Esp. Ceram. y Vidr* 54 (2015) 11–20, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsecv.2015.02.003>.
- [6] M. Belay Getahun, E. Budi Santiko, T. Imae, C.L. Chiang, Y.G. Lin, Photocatalytic conversion of gaseous carbon dioxide to methanol on CuO/ZnO-embedded carbohydrate polymer films, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 604 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2022.154515>.
- [7] B. Srikanth, R. Goutham, R. Badri Narayan, A. Ramprasad, K.P. Gopinath, A. R. Sankaranarayanan, Recent advancements in supporting materials for immobilised photocatalytic applications in waste water treatment, *J. Environ. Manage.* 200 (2017) 60–78, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.05.063>.
- [8] K. Abe, Enhancement of photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films by electrochemical reduction, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.* 16 (2021) 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.20964/2021.10.10>.
- [9] N.L. Tarwal, A.V. Rajgure, A.I. Inamdar, R.S. Devan, I.Y. Kim, S.S. Suryavanshi, Y. R. Ma, J.H. Kim, P.S. Patil, Growth of multifunctional ZnO thin films by spray pyrolysis technique, *Sens. Actuat., A Phys* 199 (2013) 67–73, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2013.05.003>.
- [10] A. Akyol, M. Bayramoglu, Photocatalytic performance of ZnO coated tubular reactor, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 180 (2010) 466–473, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.04.053>.
- [11] P. Jongnavakit, P. Amornpitoksuk, S. Suwanboon, T. Ratana, Surface and photocatalytic properties of ZnO thin film prepared by sol-gel method, *Thin Solid Films* 520 (2012) 5561–5567, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2012.04.050>.
- [12] M. Addamo, V. Augugliaro, A. Di Paola, E. García-López, V. Loddo, G. Marci, L. Palmisano, Photocatalytic thin films of TiO₂ formed by a sol-gel process using titanium tetraisopropoxide as the precursor, *Thin Solid Films* 516 (2008) 3802–3807, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2007.06.139>.
- [13] A. Di Mauro, M.E. Fragalà, V. Privitera, G. Impellizzeri, ZnO for application in photocatalysis: from thin films to nanostructures, *Mater. Sci. Semicond. Process.* 69 (2017) 44–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2017.03.029>.
- [14] R.S. Pedaneekar, S.K. Shaikh, K.Y. Rajpure, Thin film photocatalysis for environmental remediation: a status review, *Curr. Appl. Phys.* 20 (2020) 931–952, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cap.2020.04.006>.
- [15] D. Fassel, S. Députier, V. Bouquet, M. Guilloux-Viry, Effect of the microstructure of ZnO thin films prepared by PLD on their performance as toxic gas sensors, *Chemosensors* 10 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemosensors10070285>.
- [16] D. Zhao, S. Sathasivam, M. Wang, C.J. Carmalt, Transparent and conducting boron doped ZnO thin films grown by aerosol assisted chemical vapor deposition, *RSC Adv.* 12 (2022) 33049–33055, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ra05895b>.
- [17] J.A. Mathew, V. Tsumra, J.M. Sajkowski, A. Wierzbicka, R. Jakiela, Y. Zhydachevskyy, E. Przewdzicka, M. Stachowicz, A. Kozanecki, Photoluminescence of Europium in ZnO and ZnMgO thin films grown by Molecular Beam Epitaxy, *J. Lumin.* 251 (2022) 0–6, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlumin.2022.119167>.
- [18] M. Kuru, H. Narsat, The effect of heat treatment temperature and Mg doping on structural and photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films fabricated by RF magnetron co-sputtering technique, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Electron.* 30 (2019) 18484–18495, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-019-02202-2>.

- [19] B. Khalfallah, I. Riahi, F. Chaabouni, Effect of Cu doping on the structural, optical and electrical properties of ZnO thin films grown by RF magnetron sputtering: application to solar photocatalysis, *Opt. Quantum Electron.* 53 (2021) 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11082-021-02861-8>.
- [20] N.V. Kaneva, G.G. Yordanov, C.D. Dushkin, Photocatalytic action of ZnO thin films prepared by the sol-gel method, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.* 98 (2009) 259–263, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11144-009-0081-6>.
- [21] V. Kumar, N. Singh, R.M. Mehra, A. Kapoor, L.P. Purohit, H.C. Swart, Role of film thickness on the properties of ZnO thin films grown by sol-gel method, *Thin Solid Film.* 539 (2013) 161–165, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2013.05.088>.
- [22] G.T. Delgado, C.I. Zúñiga Romero, S.A. Mayén Hernández, R. Castanedo Pérez, O. Z. Angel, Optical and structural properties of the sol-gel-prepared ZnO thin films and their effect on the photocatalytic activity, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cell.* 93 (2009) 55–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2008.03.020>.
- [23] A.L.T. Zheng, C.A.C. Abdullah, E.L.T. Chung, Y. Andou, Recent progress in visible light-doped ZnO photocatalyst for pollution control, *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 20 (2023) 5753–5772, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-022-04354-x>.
- [24] R. Kumar Patnaik, N. Divya, A brief review on the synthesis of TiO₂ thin films and its application in dye degradation, *Mater. Today Proc.* 72 (2023) 2749–2756, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.10.064>.
- [25] J. Lv, W. Gong, K. Huang, J. Zhu, F. Meng, X. Song, Z. Sun, Effect of annealing temperature on photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films prepared by sol-gel method, *Superlatt. Microstruct.* 50 (2011) 98–106, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spmi.2011.05.003>.
- [26] K. Thongsuriwong, P. Amornpitoksuk, S. Suwanboon, Structure, morphology, photocatalytic and antibacterial activities of ZnO thin films prepared by sol-gel dip-coating method, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 24 (2013) 275–280, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apt.2012.07.002>.
- [27] M. Toubane, R. Tala-Ighil, F. Bensouici, M. Bououdina, W. Cai, S. Liu, M. Souier, A. Iratni, Structural, optical and photocatalytic properties of ZnO nanorods: effect of aging time and number of layers, *Ceram. Int.* 42 (2016) 9673–9685, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2016.03.056>.
- [28] F. Atay, O. Gultepe, The effect of spinning cycle on structural, optical, surface and photocatalytic properties of sol-gel derived ZnO films, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 100 (2021) 299–309, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-021-05661-4>.
- [29] M.V. Roldán, Y. Castro, N. Pellegrini, A. Durán, Enhanced photocatalytic activity of mesoporous SiO₂/TiO₂ sol-gel coatings doped with Ag nanoparticles, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 76 (2015) 180–194, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-015-3765-6>.
- [30] Y. Castro, A. Durán, Ca doping of mesoporous TiO₂ films for enhanced photocatalytic efficiency under solar irradiation, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 78 (2016) 482–491, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-016-3988-1>.
- [31] L. Spanhel, M.A. Anderson, Semiconductor Clusters in the Sol-Gel Process: Quantized Aggregation, Gelation, and Crystal Growth in Concentrated ZnO Colloids, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 113 (1991) 2826–2833, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00008a004>.
- [32] M. Vafaei, M.S. Ghamsari, Preparation and characterization of ZnO nanoparticles by a novel sol-gel route, *Mater. Lett.* 61 (2007) 3265–3268.
- [33] M.S. Tokumoto, V. Briois, C.V. Santilli, S.H. Pulcinelli, Preparation of ZnO Nanoparticles: structural Study, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* (2003) 547–551.
- [34] S. Bandyopadhyay, G.K. Paul, R. Roy, S.K. Sen, S. Sen, Study of structural and electrical properties of grain-boundary modified ZnO films prepared by sol-gel technique, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 74 (2002) 83–91, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0254-0584\(01\)00402-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0254-0584(01)00402-3).
- [35] D.R. Rout, H.M. Jena, Polyethylene glycol functionalized reduced graphene oxide coupled with zinc oxide composite adsorbent for removal of phenolic wastewater, *Environ. Res.* (2022) 214, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114044>.
- [36] D.M. Smilgies, Scherrer grain-size analysis adapted to grazing-incidence scattering with area detectors, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 42 (2009) 1030–1034, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889809040126>.
- [37] J. Kennedy, P.P. Murnu, J. Leveueur, A. Markwitz, J. Futter, Controlling preferred orientation and electrical conductivity of zinc oxide thin films by post growth annealing treatment, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 367 (2016) 52–58, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2016.01.160>.
- [38] N. Ashkenov, B.N. Mbenkum, C. Bundesmann, V. Riede, M. Lorenz, D. Spemann, E. M. Kaidashev, A. Kasic, M. Schubert, M. Grundmann, G. Wagner, H. Neumann, V. Darakchieva, H. Arwin, B. Monemar, Infrared dielectric functions and phonon modes of high-quality ZnO films, *J. Appl. Phys.* 93 (2003) 126–133, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1526935>.
- [39] K. Kara, E.Ş. Tüzemen, R. Esen, Annealing effects of ZnO thin films on p-Si(100) substrate deposited by PFCVD, *Turk. J. Phys.* 38 (2014) 238–244, <https://doi.org/10.3906/fiz-1310-3>.
- [40] Z.R. Tian, J.A. Voigt, J. Liu, B. McKenzie, M.J. Mcdermott, M.A. Rodriguez, H. Konishi, H. Xu, Complex and oriented ZnO nanostructures, *Nat. Mater.* 2 (2003) 821–826, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat1014>.
- [41] K. Kaviyarasu, C. Maria Magdalan, K. Kanimozhi, J. Kennedy, B. Siddhardha, E. Subba Reddy, N.K. Rotte, C.S. Sharma, F.T. Thema, D. Letsholathebe, G.T. Mola, M. Maaza, Elucidation of photocatalysis, photoluminescence and antibacterial studies of ZnO thin films by spin coating method, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B Biol.* 173 (2017) 466–475, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2017.06.026>.
- [42] W. Yang, J. Liu, Z. Guan, Z. Liu, B. Chen, L. Zhao, Y. Li, X. Cao, X. He, C. Zhang, Q. Zeng, Y. Fu, Morphology, electrical and optical properties of magnetron sputtered porous ZnO thin films on Si (100) and Si (111) substrates, *Ceram. Int.* 46 (2020) 6605–6611.
- [43] S. Singh, P. Chakrabarti, Comparison of the structural and optical properties of ZnO thin films deposited by three different methods for optoelectronic applications, *Superlatt. Microstruct.* 64 (2013) 283–293, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spmi.2013.09.031>.
- [44] N. Mediouni, chantal guillard, F. Dappozze, L. Khrouz, S. Parola, C. Colbeau-Justin, A.B.H. Amara, H. Ben Rhaïem, nicole jaffrezic-renault, P. Namour, Impact of structural defects on the photocatalytic properties of ZnO, *SSRN Electron. J.* 6 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4040407>.
- [45] V. Gurylev, T.P. Perng, Defect engineering of ZnO: review on oxygen and zinc vacancies, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 41 (2021) 4977–4996, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2021.03.031>.
- [46] J. Wang, R. Chen, L. Xiang, S. Komarneni, Synthesis, properties and applications of ZnO nanomaterials with oxygen vacancies: a review, *Ceram. Int.* 44 (2018) 7357–7377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.02.013>.
- [47] D. Chen, Z. Wang, T. Ren, H. Ding, W. Yao, R. Zong, Y. Zhu, Influence of defects on the photocatalytic activity of ZnO, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118 (2014) 15300–15307, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp5033349>.
- [48] L.J. Meng, C.P. Moreira de Sá, M.P. dos Santos, Study of the structural properties of ZnO thin films by x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 78 (1994) 57–61, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-4332\(94\)90031-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-4332(94)90031-0).
- [49] K.R. Murali, Properties of sol-gel dip-coated zinc oxide thin films, *J. Phys. Chem. Solid.* 68 (2007) 2293–2296, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpcs.2007.06.006>.
- [50] N. Shakti, T. Mandal, A. Prakash, G. Purohit, Annealing temperature tuned structural and impedance properties of ZnO thin films, *Surface. Interface.* 9 (2017) 228–232, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2017.10.004>.
- [51] U. Chaitra, D. Kekuda, K.M. Rao, Effect of annealing temperature on the evolution of structural, microstructural, and optical properties of spin coated ZnO thin films, *Ceram. Int.* 43 (2017) 7115–7122, <https://doi.org/10.1097/JU.0000000000002945>.
- [52] N. Bouhssira, S. Abed, E. Tomasella, J. Cellier, A. Mosbah, Influence of annealing temperature on the properties of ZnO thin films deposited by thermal evaporation, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 252 (2006) 5594–5597, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2005.12.134>.
- [53] A. López-Suárez, D. Acosta, C. Magaña, F. Hernández, Optical, structural and electrical properties of ZnO thin films doped with Mn, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Electron.* 31 (2020) 7389–7397, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-019-02830-8>.
- [54] A. Hafidallah, A. Ferdi, M.S. Aida, N. Attaf, A. Amara, Effect of substrate temperature studies on spray pyrolysis deposited ZnO thin films, *Int. J. Adv. Res.* 3 (2015) 240–246.
- [55] S.M. Saleh, Metal oxide nanomaterials as photo-catalyst for dye degradation, *Res. Dev. Mater. Sci.* 9 (2019) 990–997, <https://doi.org/10.31031/rdms.2019.09.000710>.
- [56] P. Dong, B. Yang, C. Liu, F. Xu, X. Xi, G. Hou, R. Shao, Highly enhanced photocatalytic activity of WO₃ thin films loaded with Pt-Ag bimetallic alloy nanoparticles, *RSC Adv.* 7 (2017) 947–956, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ra25272a>.
- [57] D. Rajamanickam, M. Shanthi, Photocatalytic degradation of an organic pollutant by zinc oxide-solar process, *Arab. J. Chem.* 9 (2016) S1858–S1868.
- [58] M.A. Rauf, S.S. Ashraf, Fundamental principles and application of heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of dyes in solution, *Chem. Eng. J.* 151 (2009) 10–18, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2009.02.026>.
- [59] M.R. Islam, M.G. Azam, Enhanced photocatalytic activity of Mg-doped ZnO thin films prepared by sol-gel method, *Surf. Eng.* 0 (2020) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02670844.2020.1801143>.
- [60] G. El Fidha, N. Bitri, F. Chaabouni, S. Acosta, Physical and photocatalytic properties of sprayed Dy doped ZnO thin films under sunlight irradiation for degrading methylene blue, *RSC Adv.* 11 (2021) 24917–24925, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ra03967a>.
- [61] B. Al Farsi, T.M. Souier, F. Al Marzuqi, M. Al Maashani, M. Bououdina, M. Widatallah, M. Al Abri, Structural and optical properties of visible active photocatalytic Al doped ZnO nanostructured thin films prepared by dip coating, *Opt. Mater. (Amst.)* 113 (2021) 110868, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2021.110868>.
- [62] U. Alam, K. Azam, D. Ali, D. Bahnemann, M. Muneer, Comparative photocatalytic activity of sol-gel derived rare earth metal (La, Nd, Sm and Dy)-doped ZnO photocatalysts for degradation of dyes, *RSC Adv.* (2018) 17582–17594, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8ra01638k>.
- [63] P. Jongnavakit, P. Amornpitoksuk, S. Suwanboon, T. Ratana, Surface and photocatalytic properties of ZnO thin film prepared by sol-gel method, *Thin Solid Film.* 520 (2012) 5561–5567, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2012.04.050>.
- [64] D. Aryanto, E. Hastuti, M. Taspika, K. Anam, I. Isnaeni, W.B. Widayatno, A. S. Wismogroho, P. Marwoto, B.W. Nuryadin, A. Noviyanto, S. Sugianto, Characteristics and photocatalytic activity of highly c-axis-oriented ZnO thin films, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 96 (2020) 226–235, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-020-05361-5>.
- [65] E.A. Daher, B. Riachi, J. Chamoun, C. Laberty-Robert, W. Hamd, New approach for designing wrinkled and porous ZnO thin films for photocatalytic applications, *Colloid. Surface. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 658 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.130628>.